

ICCM 24 Baltimore, Maryland | 4.-8. August 2025

Understanding Towpreg Manufacturing – Combining Advanced Resin Formulation and Improved Processing Techniques for the Next Generation of Pressure Vessels

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INTRODUCTION

Digitalization for Sustainability

- **Lack of digital predictability** of EV components necessitates validation
- Hardware- and resource-intensive in **conflict with sustainability objectives**

Project duration: 1.1.2023-31.12.2025
Total project volume ~ 38 mio Euro
28 Project partners

Next generation of hydrogen pressure vessel

HDPE/PA – thermoplastic liner acts as hydrogen barrier

Simpler/cheaper manufacturing process

10-20% lighter than type IV vessels

Improved exploitation of **vessel space**

Development of optimized composite for permeation reduction

Manufacturing methods

Wet-winding (state of the art)

- Low viscosity
- Winding speed up to **60 m/min**
- Variation in FVC

Towpreg winding

- High viscosity.
- Winding speed up to **240 m/min**
- Pre-impregnated products allow precise FVC control

Towpreg winding improves process precision significantly

Next generation of hydrogen pressure vessel

Permeability of different polymers at varying temperature:

Crack formation in composite leads to permeation pathways – crack initiation and reduction necessary

Polymers for Hydrogen Infrastructure and Vehicle Fuel Systems, Barth 2013;
 Damage and permeability in linerless composite cryogenic tanks, David M. Grogan 2015

Manufacturing and material challenges

Type V

Challenges:

Cracks in composite due to mechanical/thermal stress might **lead to leakage**

Optimisation of manufacturing to **avoid defects**

wet-wound structure

- How can we improve the composite material to minimize crack formation/propagation?
- How can we improve the manufacturing process to reduce irregularities and defects?

OVERVIEW

Development of Type V resin systems for pressure vessels

Optimizing process control for Towpreg manufacturing

Mechanical testing of filament wound composites

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Tensile properties of resin systems

2 Formulations:

- Latent hardener + Curing agent
- Similar viscosity profile

Digitow-1:
 DGEBA_(low visc.):DGEBA_(high visc.)
 T_G: 140 °C

Digitow-2:
 50:50 DGEBA_(low visc.):Novolak
 T_G: 160 °C

Toughening agent:

- Polysiloxane block copolymer (**BCP**)

Resin fracture mechanics

Digitow-1 –
medium T_G
 T_G : 140 °C

Digitow-2 –
high T_G
 T_G : 160 °C

- Comparable K_{IC}
- Plateau for Digitow-2

- G_{IC} – benefits from higher BCP concentrations

- More ductile resin allows significantly higher toughening – despite minor E differences
- 3 % BCP sweet spot between mechanical + fracture mechanical properties

Fatigue crack propagation

Crack propagation

- ASTM E647-2
- Curves from single specimen
- Following crack propagation through mechanical signal

Potential synergistic effects combining BCP + SiO₂-NP ?

BCP decreases crack growth significantly up to 5 wt%

Overview

Development of Type V resin systems for pressure vessels

Optimizing process control for Towpreg manufacturing

Mechanical testing of filament wound composites

Modifications of the winder unit – SC filament winder (ETC)

Width measurement

Fiber tension measurement

Fiber tension up to 100 N / Roving measurable

Consistent unwinding process – consistent impregnation process

Modifications of the winder unit

Impregnation

Low heat transfer

More stable and precise parameter tuning possible

How to manufacture Towpregs?

Winding tension

- Low roving tension < 1350 cN
- Tension too high:

Rovings “merge”

After winding

2 h @ RT

70 °C

85 °C

Impregnation temperature

- Low enough to allow consistent impregnation
- High enough to avoid dewetting

Winding pattern

- Low winding angles < 70 ° show increase in fiber rupture due to uptake of underlying filaments

Sweet spots in fiber tension and impregnation temperature to be found!

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Mechanical testing of filament wound composites

Mechanical testing of composite specimens

NOL-split disk (tensile) testing

Naval Ordnance Laboratory,
White Oak Maryland

oven + shrink tape

Optimization of winding parameters necessary

ISO-527/5 – 0°

Digitow-2 reaches expected 0°-strength

Summary

Successful toughening of
Towpreg resin systems ✓

Impregnation process
successfully monitored ✓

Mechanical testing of filament
wound structures successful ✓

Outlook

? Transfer of fracture toughness
to composite level

? Can the optimization of
processing parameters improve
the mechanical performance

Questions?

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Project:

Digitain - FKZ: 19S22006Q

Special thanks to:

Federal ministry for economic affairs and energy

For the financial support

Olin Corporation for the supply of resin

